

DEPRESSION AS A PREDICTOR OF SUICIDE AND SUICIDAL IDEATION AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF JOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study explored depression as a predictor of suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos, Nigeria. A cross-sectional research design was used, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods, with data collected from 236 participants. Most participants were between 20-25 years old (94.2%), male (55.8%), and single (78.4%). Religious affiliations were primarily Christian (73.1%), followed by Muslim (26.9%). Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire adapted from the Depression Inventory (DI) and Beck Suicide Scale (BSS). Three hypotheses were tested using one-way ANOVA and regression analysis at a 0.005 significance level. Results indicated that 93% of participants experienced depression, significantly predicting suicide and suicidal ideation ($p = 0.0005$). Depression explained 84.3% of the variance in suicidal ideation ($t = 15.846$, $p = 0.0005$). Socio-demographic factors, particularly religious affiliation (33.1%, $p = 0.001$), significantly influenced suicidal ideation. These findings highlight the need for educational programs addressing depression and suicide awareness among medical students.

Keywords: Depression, Suicide, Suicidal Ideation, Medical Students

Introduction

The rising incidence of depression and suicidal ideation among students is a global concern. Every year, nearly 1 million people die by suicide, and over the last 45 years, the global suicide rate has increased by 60% (Ricardo & Carlos, 2018). Suicide ranks as the second leading cause of death among young people, following road traffic accidents. Medical students are considered a high-risk group for suicide (Shanafelt et al., 2011; Schruhammer et al., 2014), and the issue often manifests during medical school. Initially, first-year medical students report similar levels of psychological distress as their non-medical peers. However, their mental health tends to deteriorate as they advance in their medical training. Depression is a primary factor linked to suicidal ideation, which is a strong indicator of suicide attempts (Sobowale, Fan, & Sherer, 2014). According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2016), depression affects approximately 350 million people worldwide (Onyishi, Talukdar, Sanchez, Olaleye, & Medavarapu, 2016). In severe cases, depression can become a chronic health issue, contributing to an estimated 800,000 deaths annually. Suicide, a severe complication of depression, is the second leading cause of death for individuals aged 15 to 29 years. Data from the Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) indicate that the average age of medical school applicants who die by suicide is 24 years (Ella, 2006). Suicidal ideation, which involves thoughts, consideration, or planning of suicide, varies widely among medical students, with rates ranging from 6% to 43% (Derogatis, Rickels, & Rocks, 1976).

Additionally, research has shown that female medical students exhibit higher rates of suicidal ideation compared to male students (Kessler & Walters, 1998). Several factors contribute to the vulnerability of medical students to suicidal ideation, including personal and professional stressors such as information overload, lack of leisure time, financial debt, being away from home, academic pressures, and work demands (Caplan, 1994). Despite having access to healthcare, medical students often avoid seeking psychiatric help due to concerns about time, confidentiality, stigma, and potential negative effects on their future careers (Garlow, Koestner et al., 2008; Ibrahim & Abdelraham, 2015). Suicidal ideation negatively impacts students' quality of life and their physical and mental well-being. However, there is limited research on suicide ideation and attempts among medical students in low- and middle-income countries.

Statement of the Problem:

In recent years, the prevalence of depression and suicide among medical students at the University of Jos has increased significantly. Within the past two years, over 50 medical students have sought treatment at the psychiatric unit of Jos University Hospital for symptoms of depression and suicidal ideation. First-year medical students typically report psychological distress levels similar to their peers in the general population, but their mental health worsens as they progress through their studies. This decline has negatively affected their academic performance and personal lives, leading to issues such as repeating academic years, changing courses or faculties, and even dropping out of school. Factors contributing to this include information overload, financial strain, academic pressure, and being away from home. Research on depression and suicidal ideation among medical students in low- and middle-income countries is limited. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate depression as a predictor of suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine depression as a primary factor contributing to suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos, Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. To assess whether depression significantly predicts suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos.
2. To evaluate the role of gender differences in depression as a contributing factor to suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos.
3. To identify the factors that contribute to depression, leading to suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested in the study:

1. Depression does not significantly predict suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos.

2. Gender differences in depression do not significantly contribute to suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos.

3. There are no significant factors contributing to depression as a leading cause of suicide and suicidal ideation among medical students at the University of Jos.

Review of Related Studies

Desaleyn, Wondic, and Addisu (2020) conducted a cross-sectional study investigating suicidal ideation, attempts, and associated factors among 393 medical students at the University of Goudar, Northwest Ethiopia. The study used a simple random sampling technique and data were collected via self-administered questionnaires. Suicidal ideation and attempts were assessed using the World Health Organization Composite International Diagnostic Interview (CIDI). The results indicated that 14% of participants experienced suicidal ideation and 7.4% reported a suicide attempt. Key risk factors for suicidal ideation included female gender, co-morbid depression, Khat chewing, and poor social support, while suicidal attempts were associated with female gender, depression, and a history of mental illness. Onyishi, Debjyoti, Sanchez, Olaleye, and Medavarapu (2016) conducted a review of 15 peer-reviewed studies examining the prevalence of clinical depression among medical students and professionals from 1980 to 2016.

The analysis showed a high prevalence of depression and burnout, particularly among medical students, leading to increased suicidal ideation. Female medical students and professionals exhibited higher levels of psychological distress compared to their male counterparts. Coentre and Gois (2018) reviewed 17 studies involving 13,244 medical students from 13 countries to assess the prevalence of suicidal ideation and associated risk factors. The prevalence ranged from 1.8% to 53.6%, with the most common factors being depression, a history of psychiatric disorders, low socioeconomic status, drug use, and feelings of neglect by parents. Aniebue and Onyema (2018) investigated the prevalence of depressive symptoms among 262 medical students at the University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus. Using the Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale, the study found a depression rate of 23.3%. Higher levels of depression were observed among younger students (ages 16-20), females, and those undergoing professional examinations. Students who smoked regularly exhibited significantly higher levels of depression compared to non-smokers.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the cognitive approach, which emphasizes the role of thought processes in the development of depression. According to this model, depression is a result of systematic negative biases in cognitive processing, leading to emotional, behavioral, and physical symptoms. The theory posits that depressed individuals think differently from non-depressed individuals, and that these cognitive distortions precede the onset of depressive mood. Therefore, addressing negative thinking patterns is key to understanding and managing depression and its potential link to suicide and suicidal ideation.

Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional research design incorporating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to collect data from a sample of 236 participants. The independent variables included depression, suicide, and suicidal ideation, while the dependent variables were assessed using the Symptom Distress Checklist and the Beck Suicide Scale. The research was conducted within the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences at the University of Jos. The University, initially established in November 1971 as a satellite campus of the University of Ibadan, is located at an elevation of 1,173 meters, with coordinates of latitude 9.9495° north and longitude 8.8895° east. Participants were drawn from 300-level students in the faculty of medical sciences. A total of 236 participants, comprising both male and female students, were selected through randomization. Initially, 250 students were randomly selected as potential participants. They were briefed on the study's purpose, informed consent was obtained, and the questionnaires were administered. Once completed, the questionnaires were retrieved and scored. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was adapted from the Depression Inventory (DI) and the Beck Suicide Scale (BSS). It was divided into three sections: Section A (six questions on biodata), Section B (ten questions assessing depression), and Section C (ten questions assessing suicidal ideation).

Data collection was conducted using both primary and secondary sources, with the Depression Inventory and Beck Suicide Scale adopted for the study. Two research assistants aided in the administration of these instruments during the students' free periods. Participants were briefed on the nature of the study, and written consent was obtained. Those who declined to participate were exempted.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

	Frequency	Percentage %
Age Group		
20-25 years	98	94.2
26-30 years	4	3.8
31-35 years	2	1.9
Gender		
Male	58	55.8
Female	46	44.2
Marital Status		
Single	80	78.4
Married	22	21.6
Religious Affiliation		
Christianity	76	73.1
Islam	28	26.9

Hypothesis Testing

HO1: There is no significant prevalence of depression among medical students at the University of Jos.

A binomial test was conducted on a random sample of 104 medical students to determine the prevalence of depression. Of these, 97 students (93%) were found to be depressed, while 7 students (7%) were not, $p = 0.0005$ ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 2: Binomial test of prevalence of depression among undergraduate medical students

2	N	Observed Proportion	Test Proportion	Exact Sig. (2-tailed)
Depressed	97	.93	.50	0.0005
Normal	7	.07		
Total	104	1.00		

HO2: Depression is not a significant predictor of suicide and suicidal ideation.

A linear regression analysis was conducted to test the hypothesis. The results of the regression model 1 summary (Table 3) revealed that the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.708$, $F_{(1, 104)} = 251.092$ (5% level of significance). This showed that the model can be held for 70.8% change in suicide and suicide ideation. The F-statistic (ANOVA) of the model had a closeness of fit which means that the model is statistically significant at 5% ($p \leq 0.05$) level of significance. Result of the regression coefficient of depression in the estimated regression line is 0.843 (Table 4) which indicates that 84.3% of variation in suicide and suicide ideation was accounted for by depression. The value of the calculated statistic of depression was significant, $t = 15.846$, $p = 0.0005$ ($p < .05$). The null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3: Model 1 Summary

R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
			R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
.711	.708	8.165	.711	251.092	1	104	0.0005

Table 4: Regression Coefficients for Hypothesis One

	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	-7.812	2.337		-3.343	.001
Depression	1.062	.067	.843	15.846	.0005

H₀₃: Socio-demographic factors are not significant predictors of suicide and suicide ideation among medical students of the University of Jos

The results of the regression model 2 summary (Table 5) revealed that the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.106$, $F_{(4, 97)} = 3.978$ (5% level of significance). This showed that the model can be held for 10.6% change in suicide and suicide ideation. The F-statistic (ANOVA) of the model had a closeness of fit which means that the model is statistically significant at 5% ($p \leq 0.05$) level of significance. Result in Table 6 shows the regression coefficients of the socio-demographic factors in the estimated regression lines. The result indicates that 8% of variation in suicide and suicide ideation was accounted for by age ($t = 0.810$, $p = 0.420$); 3.2% of variation in suicide and suicide ideation was accounted for by gender ($t = 0.332$, $p = 0.740$); 10.7% of variation in suicide and suicide ideation was accounted for by marital status ($t = 1.058$, $p = 0.293$); and 33.1% of variation in suicide and suicide ideation was significantly accounted for by religious affiliation ($t = 3.324$, $p = 0.001$).

Table 5: Model 2 Summary

R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
			R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.
							F Change

.141 .106 14.298 .141 3.978 4 97 0.005

Table 6: Regression Coefficients of Hypothesis Three

	Unstandardized		Standardize		Sig.
	Coefficients		d	t	
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	13.567	8.117		1.672	.098
Age	-3.586	4.426	-.080	-.810	.420
Gender	-.978	2.944	-.032	-.332	.740
Marital status	3.917	3.704	.107	1.058	.293
Religious affiliation	11.166	3.359	.331	3.324	.001

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study demonstrated that out of 104 respondents, 97 (93%) were identified as experiencing depression, while 7 (7%) did not report depressive symptoms. Linear regression analysis yielded significant results, indicating a robust relationship between depression and suicidal ideation. This outcome aligns with the research by Onyishi et al. (2016), which conducted a comprehensive review of 15 peer-reviewed articles published from 1980 to 2016. Their review indicates a rising trend in depression prevalence, particularly among medical students, and highlights its association with increased levels of burnout and suicidal ideation, which are common among residents and attending physicians. Similarly, a study by Mackenzie et al. (2012) in the Midwest and Northwest regions of North America found comparable depression rates among men (25%) and women (26%). The data also revealed a logarithmic increase in suicidal ideation correlating with rising depression rates among medical students.

Specifically, age accounted for 8% of the variance in suicidal ideation, while mental status contributed 3%, and religious affiliation explained a significant 33.1%. This suggests a direct

relationship where a higher incidence of depression leads to increased suicidal thoughts. Factors contributing to this trend among medical students include burnout, excessive information load, lack of leisure time, financial pressures, separation from home, and work-related stress (Caplan, 1994). There is a notable rise in depression and suicide rates among medical students at the University of Jos. Over the past two years, more than 50 medical students have sought treatment at the psychiatric unit of Jos University Teaching Hospital for symptoms of depression and suicidal ideation. Initially, first-year medical students exhibited psychological morbidity rates comparable to their age-matched peers in the general population; however, their mental health deteriorated as they advanced in their medical studies (Sobowale et al., 2014).

Conclusions

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), depression is a global concern affecting approximately 350 million people (WHO, 2006) and can evolve into severe health issues, particularly in chronic cases, leading to approximately 800,000 suicides annually. Depression is characterized by pervasive feelings of worthlessness and hopelessness. It is the second leading cause of death among individuals aged 15 to 29 years (WHO, 2006). The Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) reported that the average age of suicide among medical school applicants is 24 years (Ella, 2006), suggesting that suicide, predominantly resulting from depression, is a significant cause of mortality in medical schools and colleges. The psychological and physical effects of depression can induce feelings of fear, diminished self-esteem, anger, and resentment among medical students (Ella, 2006).

Clinical depression symptoms are also prevalent among practicing physicians, with gender differences indicating a higher prevalence in women. Numerous studies conducted among medical students using various assessment tools have corroborated these findings. Despite having access to healthcare, many medical students are hesitant to seek psychiatric assistance. Concerns regarding time, confidentiality, stigma, and potential negative career repercussions contribute to the under-treatment of mental health issues within this demographic (Coentre et al., 2018). Understanding the prevalence and determinants of suicidal ideation in medical students can facilitate early detection and intervention, thereby alleviating the severity of these issues. Moreover, intervening during the early stages of medical training could potentially reduce the risk of suicide as students transition into practicing physicians.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed:

1. Future research should control for confounding variables, including comorbid medical, psychological, and cognitive issues.
2. Subsequent studies could benefit from larger sample sizes and broader inclusivity across different year groups within the medical school to enhance the generalizability of the findings.
3. The necessity for ongoing education and awareness regarding mental health issues among medical students cannot be overstated. The University of Jos administration should enhance efforts to raise awareness about the issues of depression and suicide, which are crucial for addressing these co-morbid disorders.
4. The administration should also consider revising the medical curriculum, as many students have expressed concerns regarding excessive workloads.

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